

[John David Kaweske](#) is an executive working in the biotechnology sector. Almost two decades he's been working closely with investment banking departments as a Managing Director of various firms. His duties included reviewing startup companies within biotech sector that could attract a financial. Kaweske has been formulating business plans for start-up companies and funding start-up companies in their early stage.

John David Kaweske has spent many years working in the biotech sector. For almost 20 years he was Managing Director of several investment firms that were starting in the biotech business. He is also a member of the Board of Directors of local and international companies and has closed a number of mergers and acquisitions.

Today, John David Kaweske works as a CEO of Bio Clean Energy S.A., the company he founded back in 2004. Bio Clean Energy S.A. is a Brazil-based company which produces and distributes renewable energy. It is one of the few contractors that sell biofuel directly to Petrobras, S.A.

Bio Clean Energy is one of the leading manufacturers of biodiesel based on alternative raw materials in Brazil, in particular from used cooking oils and other raw materials with a high Fatty acid content. The first production plant started in 2006 with a capacity of 12,000 tons. Since September 2009 it has a capacity of 85,000 tons for the production of biodiesel. Bio Clean Energy biodiesel complies with the American quality standard D6751-08.